

ASYMPTOTIC STATISTICS FOR WAVENUMBER ESTIMATION

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ABSTRACT

The use of an array of sensors for determining the properties of propagating waves is of considerable importance in many applications. For example, in radar and sonar, an array of sensors is used to determine the spectral content and spatial coordinates of targets. In many situations estimates of the spectral and spatial parameters are based on the estimated cross-spectral matrix. In this paper we establish asymptotic distributional properties for wavenumber estimates using the asymptotic statistical properties of eigenvalues and eigenvectors of smoothed cross-spectral matrix estimates.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consider an arbitrary three-dimensional array of point receiving sensors. The array is in a medium with a three-dimensional noise field and, using spectral estimation methods, is used to estimate the vector velocity, or wavenumber, of propagating waves in the medium.

It is well known that a stationary random process can be characterized by means of a spectral density function. This function provides information concerning the power as a function of frequency. In a similar manner, propagating waves in a homogeneous random field can be characterized by a frequency-wavenumber spectral density function. This function provides information concerning the power as a function of frequency and the vector velocity of the propagating waves. In this paper we consider the situation where the frequency is assumed to be known and consider estimation of the wavenumber spectra only.

We assume that the array consists of M omnidirectional sensors; we let $\Phi(\omega)$ be the $M \times M$ cross-spectral matrix for the array at frequency ω . Its estimate will be denoted by $\hat{\Phi}^N(\omega)$. A variety of frequency-wavenumber estimators, some based on the estimated cross-spectral matrix, has been proposed, see [1], [2], and [3]. In this paper we consider a generalized form of the frequency-wavenumber estimator, and develop asymptotic statistics for this estimator. Our estimate is similar to that proposed by Pisarenko [3] except for the fact that our estimate is based on the more standard smoothed cross-spectral matrix estimate and we eliminate the Gaussian assumption on the process imposed in [3].

In Section II we present the standard estimate of the smoothed cross-spectral matrix. We also present the form of the generalized frequency-wavenumber estimate. In Section III we present Brillinger's [4] results on asymptotic statistics for eigenvector and eigenvalue estimates for smoothed cross-spectral density matrix estimates. We also present our results on asymptotic statistics for a generalized wavenumber estimate. In Section IV we comment on the dependence of the asymptotic variance on array configuration and the eigenvalues of the cross-spectral matrix.

II. THE GENERALIZED WAVENUMBER ESTIMATE

We assume that the output of a sensor, say the j^{th} located at the vector position \underline{x}_j , is a wide sense stationary discrete-time random process with zero mean. We denote the output process for the j^{th} sensor by $\{z_{j,n}\}_{n=-\infty}^{\infty}$.

Given a finite set of observations for the j^{th} sensor output process, $\{z_{j,n}\}_{n=1}^N$, we form the discrete Fourier transform

$$\hat{\gamma}_j^N(2\pi m/N) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} z_{j,n} \exp(-i2\pi nm/N) \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

and for a pair of sensors, say j and k , we calculate the second order periodogram

$$\hat{\Gamma}_{j,k}^N(2\pi m/N) = (1/2\pi N) \hat{\gamma}_j^N(2\pi m/N) \hat{\gamma}_k^N(2\pi m/N)^*$$

and the smoothed cross-spectral density estimate

$$\hat{\Phi}_{j,k}^N(\omega) = (2\pi/N) \sum_{m=1}^N a^N(\omega - 2\pi m/N) \hat{\Gamma}_{j,k}^N(2\pi m/N)$$

where $a(\alpha)$, $-\infty < \alpha < \infty$, is a weight function such that

$$a^N(\alpha) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} a[M_N(\alpha + 2\pi m)]$$

with $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} a(\alpha) d\alpha = 1$ and $\int |a(\alpha)| d\alpha < \infty$. M_N (bandwidth parameter) is a sequence of positive numbers such that $M_N \rightarrow \infty$ and $M_N/N \rightarrow 0$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$. The cross-spectral density matrix estimate is given by

$$\hat{\Phi}^N(\omega) = \left[\hat{\phi}_{j,k}^N(\omega) \right]_{\substack{j=1,2,\dots,M \\ k=1,2,\dots,M}} \quad (1)$$

We note that many authors in order to simplify the analysis do not take the weight function, $a(\alpha)$, into account in their estimate. Even though it complicates the evaluation of asymptotic statistics it must be included in order to achieve a consistent estimate of the cross-spectral density matrix.

Since $\Phi(\omega)$ is a Hermitian matrix, the usual eigenvalue and eigenvector decomposition applies and we can write

$$\Phi(\omega) = \sum_{j=1}^M \mu_j(\omega) \underline{U}_j(\omega) \underline{U}_j^*(\omega) \quad (2a)$$

and

$$\hat{\Phi}^N(\omega) = \sum_{j=1}^M \hat{\nu}_j(\omega) \hat{\underline{V}}_j(\omega) \hat{\underline{V}}_j^*(\omega) \quad (2b)$$

where $\{\mu_j(\omega)\}_{j=1}^M$ and $\{\underline{U}_j(\omega)\}_{j=1}^M$ are the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of $\Phi(\omega)$. The sets $\{\hat{\nu}_j(\omega)\}_{j=1}^M$ and $\{\hat{\underline{V}}_j(\omega)\}_{j=1}^M$ are the estimated quantities.

Now let $g(z)$ be an analytic function on the halfplane $\text{Re}(z) > 0$ and monotonically increasing function of x for $x > 0$, define $G(x) = g^{-1}(x)$, then $G(z)$ is also analytic for $\text{Re}(z) > 0$ and monotonically increasing function of x for $x > 0$.

We now define the generalized wavenumber estimate at frequency ω as $\hat{P}^N(\omega, \underline{\kappa})$ by

$$\hat{P}^N(\omega, \underline{\kappa}) = G \left\{ \underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}}^* g[\hat{\Phi}^N(\omega)] \underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where the "steering" vector $\underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}}^*$ is given by

$$\underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}}^* = [w_1 \exp(-i\underline{\kappa} \cdot \underline{x}_1), w_2 \exp(-i\underline{\kappa} \cdot \underline{x}_2), \dots, w_M \exp(-i\underline{\kappa} \cdot \underline{x}_M)] \quad (4)$$

and the set $\{w_j\}_{j=1}^M$ is wavenumber window weights, the set $\{\underline{x}_j\}_{j=1}^M$ is sensor position vectors, and $\underline{\kappa}$ is the wavenumber vector, $\underline{\kappa} = (\omega/c)\underline{r}$, \underline{r} is a vector in the direction of a propagating wave and c is the velocity of propagation.

Using the eigen-decomposition of (2b) we can rewrite the generalized wavenumber estimate $\hat{P}^N(\omega, \underline{\kappa})$ of (3) as

$$\hat{P}^N(\omega, \underline{\kappa}) = G \left\{ \underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}}^* \left[\sum_{j=1}^M g(\hat{\nu}_j(\omega)) \hat{\underline{V}}_j(\omega) \hat{\underline{V}}_j^*(\omega) \right] \underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Letting $g(x) = x$ in (5) yields the conventional wavenumber estimate, that is

$$\hat{P}^N(\omega, \underline{\kappa}) = \underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}}^* \left[\sum_{j=1}^M \hat{\nu}_j(\omega) \hat{\underline{V}}_j(\omega) \hat{\underline{V}}_j^*(\omega) \right] \underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}} \quad (6)$$

If we let $g(x) = 1/x$ in (5), we obtain the minimum energy estimate of Capon [1], that is

$$\hat{P}^N(\omega, \underline{\kappa}) = \left\{ \underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}}^* \left[\sum_{j=1}^M (1/\hat{\nu}_j(\omega)) \hat{\underline{V}}_j(\omega) \hat{\underline{V}}_j^*(\omega) \right] \underline{D}_{\underline{\kappa}} \right\}^{-1} \quad (7)$$

In the next section we examine asymptotic statistics for the generalized estimate of (5).

III. ASYMPTOTIC STATISTICS

In order to estimate the asymptotic statistics of the generalized wavenumber estimator of (5) we rely on the asymptotic statistics for eigenvalues and eigenvectors of smoothed cross-spectral matrices as developed by Brillinger [4].

We define the vector $\underline{\theta}(\omega)$ and its estimate $\hat{\underline{\theta}}^N(\omega)$ by

$$\underline{\theta}(\omega) = [\mu_1(\omega), \dots, \mu_M(\omega), \underline{U}_1(\omega), \dots, \underline{U}_M(\omega)] \quad (8a)$$

$$\hat{\underline{\theta}}^N(\omega) = [\hat{\nu}_1(\omega), \dots, \hat{\nu}_M(\omega), \hat{\underline{V}}_1(\omega), \dots, \hat{\underline{V}}_M(\omega)] \quad (8b)$$

The following assumption on the summability of all order cumulants of the processes $z_{j,n}$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, M$ is a fundamental assumption of Brillinger [4] required for establishing asymptotic statistics for second order periodograms.

Assumption 1: All order cumulants of $z_{j,n}$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, M$, satisfy

$$\sum_{r_1=-\infty}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{r_{m-1}=-\infty}^{\infty} \{1 + |r_j|\} |c_{b_1, \dots, b_m}(r_1, \dots, r_{m-1})| < \infty$$

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- [5] R.J. Serfling, Approximation Theorems of Mathematical Statistics. New York, NY: Wiley and Son, Inc., 1980.